

Quantum Spin as an Operator on a Physical State which Replaces Vector Operations? Part II

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In Part I, we considered spin as arising from a desire to replace vector operators (cross product, dot product) in a quadratic equation (continuity equation for a photon, Klein-Gordon equation for a spin .5 particle with rest mass). Here we focus on spin .5 particles and consider the Lorentz invariant: $A = -Et + px$.

If the x-axis lies along the direction of p , then E and p appear as two scalar numbers. If one, however, rotates the co-ordinate system, $E \rightarrow E$, but $p \rightarrow (p_x, p_y, p_z)$, and $t \rightarrow t$, but $x \rightarrow (x, y, z)$. The Lorentz invariant becomes: $A = -Et + p(x)x + p(y)y + p(z)z$. In other words, $p(x)$ is multiplied by x etc, there is no mixing of $p(x)$ with say y .

In the case of $-Et + px$ with p along x , one has a sum of two numbers $-Et$ and px , each being the product of two numbers. Under rotation, one still has the scalar $-Et$, but px is now $p \cdot r$. One may ask: If E multiplied by t remains a scalar composed of the product of two scalars, why does one need to introduce a vector dot product, i.e. $px \rightarrow p \cdot r$. Why does not one still have a product of two numbers, just like the Et or px case? In other words, if one wishes to have symmetry between Et and px , a rotation should not break this symmetry. A rotation does, however, occur and $p \rightarrow (p_x, p_y, p_z)$ and $x \rightarrow (x, y, z)$. One may suggest seeking generalized numbers (showing the rotation) which keep the form px i.e. the form of two generalized numbers multiplied together. (These arguments apply just as well to the Lorentz invariant $-E^2 + p^2 = -m^2 c^4$), but $-Et + px$ shows the coordinate system explicitly in that it contains x and we focus on it here).

In other words, we argue that symmetry arguments applied to $-Et + px$ suggest one should look for generalized numbers s_x, s_y, s_z such that: $p \rightarrow A + p_x s_x + p_y s_y + p_z s_z$ and $x \rightarrow B = x s_x + y s_y + z s_z$ with A multiplied by B yields $p(x)x + p(y)y + p(z)z$. The set s_x, s_y, s_z cannot be whole numbers, but matrices do solve the problem (in particular the Pauli matrices (1)). In other words, $p(x)$ is really associated with a matrix s_x and x as well. Lorentz invariants are quadratic and so if $s_x s_x = s_y s_y = s_z s_z = 1$, one does not see the presence of the s matrix. If one really has $p(x) s_x$ (etc), then given that px is a number, there is a lack of symmetry because s_x should be a property as well. A matrix, however, does not seem to be a property, but rather an operator. One may thus postulate the existence of an operator P , which yields the px numerical value, associated with s_x which is also an operator. Given that s_x is introduced to deal with co-ordinate rotations, one might expect its associated state to be related to rotations, although it is not clear specifically how. Experimentally, it is seen that a particle with spin .5 couples to a B_z magnetic field, suggesting a degree of freedom associated with current (i.e. with some kind of rotational or angular motion of charge) in one direction or the other, consistent with a 2-vector eigenvector of s_z (the Pauli matrix s_z).

Dirac Approach to the Klein-Gordon Equation

The Klein-Gordon follows from the Lorentz invariant:

$$-EE+pp = -momo \quad (c=1) \quad ((1))$$

In quantum mechanics, $E \rightarrow i \hbar \frac{d}{dt}$ partial and $p \rightarrow \hbar/i \text{ grad}$. Dirac decided to linearize this quadratic equation and found that matrices were needed (i.e. S_x, S_y, S_z) multiplied with p_x, p_y, p_z . He dealt with 4x4 matrices linked to the Pauli 2x2 matrices. We ask: What is the a priori reason for linearizing equation ((1)). (One may note that many people were aware of the quadratic form ((1)), but only Dirac, apparently, linearized it.) We suggest that linearization may have something to do with symmetry. E is a scalar, so EE is the product of two scalars, regardless of the rotation of the x, y, z co-ordinate system. If p lies along x , the pp is also the product of two numbers, but if one rotates the co-ordinate system, then $pp \rightarrow p \cdot p$. This is now a vector dot product which yields a scalar value. To have complete symmetry between E and p , one may insist on $p \cdot p$ being replaced the product of two generalized numbers.

-Et+px Considerations

Although we considered $-EE+pp$ above, one may just as well consider the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$. We use this because it explicitly contains x, y, z . We suggest that like above, Et is the product of two numbers and if p lies along x , px is the product of two numbers. If one rotates the co-ordinate system, then:

$$P \rightarrow p_x, p_y, p_z \quad ((2a)) \quad \text{and} \quad x \rightarrow (x, y, z) \quad ((2b))$$

Why should there be a symmetry break between E and t appearing as the product of two numbers and px also being the product of two numbers for p lying along x with $p \cdot r$? The case of p lying along x is the case of a special orientation of the co-ordinate system. Rotating the co-ordinate system should not cause any changes in the sense that one has two numbers multiplied together. In other words, one may argue that one does not need to use vector operations to create a scalar, i.e. the dot product in $p \cdot r$. One may note that issues appear here because there is a co-ordinate system associated with a p vector and r vector, but none with E and t .

Treating all terms as numbers means one may eliminate the notion of vectors in order to retain a sense of symmetry between $-Et$ and $p \cdot r$. This, however, means using a set of generalized numbers, i.e. whole numbers do not suffice. Matrices, however, may be considered to be generalized numbers, although they also act on vectors which is discussed later. At this point, we seek matrices as generalized numbers, linked to the rotation of the co-ordinate system i.e.

$$p \rightarrow p_x s_x + p_y s_y + p_z s_z \quad \text{and} \quad x \rightarrow x s_x + y s_y + z s_z \quad ((3)) \quad \text{such that:}$$

$$S_x s_x = s_y s_y = s_z s_z = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad s_x s_y + s_y s_x = s_x s_z + s_z s_x = s_y s_z + s_z s_y = 0 \quad ((4))$$

In such a case, the matrices s_x, s_y, s_z carry out the work of the dot product as noted in Part I. They, however, allow one to keep px as the product of two generalized number like objects i.e. ((3)).

It is well-known that the Pauli matrices satisfy ((3)). Their form is given in (1).

Px sx etc: Number Multiplied by a Generalized Number?

There is still an issue with multiplying $p(x)$ a number by s_x , a generalized number or matrix. The same holds for $p(y) s_y$ and $p(z) s_z$. A matrix is an operator, but $p(x)$ is a number. One may postulate that there should exist an operator which yields $p(x)$, the number. In such a case, s_x is an operator (associated with co-ordinate rotations) which acts on a 2-vector (spinor) and another operator acts on a function to yield $p(x)$. This function is $\exp(ip(x) \cdot x)$ and the operator is $-i\hbar/dx$. In three dimensions, one has: $\exp(i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ and $-i\hbar \text{grad}$. This result follows from free particle quantum mechanics and is not derived here. We simply wish to indicate that there is a function corresponding to an operator which yields $p(x)$ and s_x an operator which acts on a spinor. Thus there is symmetry.

Meaning of the Spinor

In the above section, we suggested that due to the asymmetry of $p(x)$, a number, multiplied by s_x , a matrix or operator, one may restore symmetry by suggesting there exist an operator which yields $p(x)$ (a number). This suggests two math functions. One is a spinor or two-vector associated with the 2×2 Pauli matrices and the other is a function which when operated upon yields $p(x)$. In other words, we started with strictly numbers (classical physics) in ((1)) and have arrived at a spinor and function linked with numbers. This suggests a different kind of physics from classical physics, based here on imposing two sets of symmetries:

- (A) There should exist a symmetry between $-E t$ (the multiplication of two numbers) and $p x$ (the multiplication of two numbers if p lies along x) even if one rotates the co-ordinate system.
- (B) Condition (A) requires the introduction of matrices as generalized numbers. These, however, also act as operators in $p(x) s_x + p(y) s_y + p(z) s_z$. We suggest one needs to impose a symmetry by replacing $p(x)$ with an operator which yields the number $p(x)$ etc.

Both the function $\exp(i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ (not derived here) and the spinors (associated with s_x, s_y, s_z) represent new physics (with respect to classical mechanics). We focus here on spin and suggest that the spinor may be related to rotation because s_x, s_y and s_z are introduced to deal with a rotation of the co-ordinate system.

Experimentally it is found that spin $1/2$ particles (electrons, nucleons etc) interact with a magnetic field, with two quantized results. The spinor (eigenvectors of the s_z Pauli matrix) accounts for this if one associates it with a kind of angular motion in one direction or the other. Thus the introduction of the matrices s_x, s_y, s_z to replace the vector operation (dot product) give rise to a physical state associated with the operator (as noted in Part I).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we suggest a reason for linearizing quadratic Lorentz invariants such as $-E^2 + p^2 = -m^2 c^4$ (as Dirac did) or $-Et + px$. We consider the latter and argue that E and t two numbers which are multiplied together as are p and x if p lies along x . This is a particular choice of the co-ordinate system. If one rotates the co-ordinate system, one needs to use the vector operator $p \cdot r$ to yield a scalar. We argue that to retain symmetry with $-Et$, one may argue for the existence of a generalized number such that: $p \rightarrow A = s_x p(x) + s_y p(y) + s_z p(z)$ and $x \rightarrow B = s_x x + s_y y + s_z z$. In such a case, one still multiplies two numbers together whether the co-ordinate system is rotated or not. Whole numbers for s_x, s_y, s_z cannot solve the problem, but 2×2 Pauli matrices can. The goal is that A multiplied by $B = p(x)p(x) + p(y)p(y) + p(z)p(z)$.

One may impose the symmetry of two generalized numbers being multiplied together for any co-ordinate system orientation. An issue which arises is that $p(x)$, $p(y)$ and $p(z)$ are numbers, while s_x , s_y and s_z are operators (matrices). To have further symmetry, one may argue for the presence of an operator which acts on a function and yields either $p(x)$, $p(y)$ or $p(z)$. We do not derive the function or operator here, but from quantum mechanics for a free particle the function is $\exp(i p \cdot r)$ and the operator $-\text{grad}$. s_x , s_y and s_z , on the other hand act on a 2-vector or spinor. We suggest that these represent physical states somehow linked to rotation as one introduced s_x , s_y and s_z to deal with the rotation of the co-ordinate system in the first place. Experiments with magnetic fields acting on charged spin $1/2$ particles seem to bear this out.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pauli_matrices